

ON ORGANO-ARSENICAL COMPOUNDS. PART III

By B. PATHAK AND T. N. GHOSH

Some N-alkylated amidines containing the arsenious acid group have now been synthesised by reacting aceto-*p*-phenetidine or acetanilide with *p*-arsanilic acid in presence of PCl_3 or POCl_3 .

In view of the promising results in the chemotherapy of filariasis, as obtained with some arsenoxide derivatives by Otto and Maren (*Science*, 1947, **106**, 105), and in view of the pronounced parasitocidal property of various amidine derivatives (King, Lourie and Yorke, *Lancet*, 1937, **233**, 136 ; Kirk and Sati, *Ann. Trop. Med. Parasitol.*, 1940, **34**, 82) it has been considered desirable to synthesise some amidine derivatives containing arsenoxide group, so that these compounds may be tested for any filaricidal activity.

Hofmann (*Jahresber. Fort. Chem.*, 1865, 414; *Monatsberichte Berl. Akad.*, 1865, p.640) obtained diphenylacetamidine and diphenylbenzamidine by condensing aniline with acetanilide and benzanilide respectively, in presence of PCl_3 or PCl_5 . This method is of general applicability and has been utilised by subsequent workers (Bamberger and Lorenzen, *Annalen*, 1893, **273**, 269 ; Hill and Robinowitz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 732 ; Sen and Ray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 646) for the synthesis of a number of new N-alkylated amidines. PCl_3 is the most suitable condensing agent for the above reaction, although P_2O_5 (Schuler, U. S. patent, 1,384, 637) or POCl_3 (Bures and Kundera, *Casopis Ceskoslov. Lekarnictva*, 1934, **14**, 272) may also be used sometimes with advantage.

By condensing aceto-*p*-phenetidine with *p*-arsanilic acid in presence of PCl_3 , the compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{OEt}$), which is an acetamidine derivative containing the arsenious acid group, has now been obtained. The isolation of the arsenious acid derivative, instead of the corresponding arsonic acid, is ascribed to the fact that PCl_3 very easily reduces arsonic acids to arsenoxides (cf. Ehrlich and Bertheim, *Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 920 ; Karrer, *Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 2275). By further reducing the compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{OEt}$) with hypophosphorus acid in presence of a trace of potassium iodide, the corresponding arseno derivative (II, $\text{R}=\text{OEt}$) has now been obtained.

The above compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{OEt}$) and an arsenic-free compound (which could not be characterised due to its poor yield) have been obtained, when the above reaction was carried out in presence of POCl_3 , instead of PCl_3 . In this connection reference is made to the reduction

of 2-chlorovinylarsonic acid to 2-chlorovinylchloroarsine by POCl_3 (Hewett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1204). The compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{OEt}$) readily decolorises iodine solution and remains unaffected when treated with sulphur dioxide in presence of potassium iodide. Moreover, in conformity with the characteristic property of arsenoxides, it dissolves in dilute caustic soda (though insoluble in aqueous bicarbonate or ammonia) solution, from which the free arsenious acid is salted out by saturating with sodium chloride. That the compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{OEt}$) is an arsenious acid and not an arsonic acid derivative has been further confirmed by reacting *p*-aminophenylarsenoxide (Ehrlich and Berthelm, *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 917) with aceto-*p*-phenetidine in presence of POCl_3 , when a compound identical with (I, $\text{R}=\text{OEt}$) has been obtained.

Similarly, by reacting acetanilide with *p*-arsanilic acid in presence of POCl_3 , a mixture of the compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{H}$) and 4-anilinoquinaldine (Conrad and Limpach, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 953; Backeberg, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2814) has been obtained. The compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{H}$) which gives all the characteristic tests of arsenious acid, as described above, has been further reduced by hypophosphorus acid in presence of potassium iodide to the arseno derivative (II, $\text{R}=\text{H}$).

EXPERIMENTAL

(Phenyl-4-ethoxy)-(phenyl-4-arsenious acid)-acetamidine (I, $\text{R}=\text{OEt}$)

(a). An intimate mixture of aceto-*p*-phenetidine (9 g.) and *p*-arsanilic acid (11 g.) was gradually added to phosphorus trichloride (60 c.c.). Heat developed and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at $100^\circ\text{--}105^\circ$ for about 4 hours. Next day, the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice, when a pasty mass was obtained. The supernatant liquid was decanted, filtered and treated with excess of ammonium hydroxide, when a solid was precipitated, which was filtered. It is soluble in alcohol and acetic acid, and sparingly in hot water, and it could not be crystallised from any of these solvents. It was therefore purified by washing with ammonium hydroxide and then trituration with 10% caustic soda solution. The alkaline solution, after treatment with charcoal, was just neutralised with hydrochloric acid, when a colorless solid (4 g.) was obtained, which shrank at 100° and melted to a brown viscous mass at $134\text{--}135^\circ$. (Found: N, 7.42; As, 19.85. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{As}$ requires N, 7.73; As, 20.70 per cent). It is readily soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid and in dilute alkali but insoluble in aqueous ammonia or bicarbonate. Its acetic acid solution readily decolorises iodine solution and it remains unaffected when its solution in dilute sulphuric acid is saturated with sulphur dioxide in presence of a trace of potassium iodide. From its solution in 10% caustic soda solution it is precipitated as such when saturated with sodium chloride.

From the pasty mass, described above, a further quantity (1 g.) of the compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{OEt}$) was obtained by trituration with 10% caustic soda solution, filtration and careful neutralisation with just the requisite quantity of hydrochloric acid. It was subsequently purified as above.

(b). The above reaction was carried out with the same quantities of the reactants in phosphorus oxychloride (60 c.c.) at $125^\circ\text{--}130^\circ$ for about 4 hours. Next day, the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice, when a pasty mass was obtained. The supernatant liquid was decanted and, when treated with excess of ammonium hydroxide, yielded a tarry mass which could not be purified. The pasty mass was washed with water and then thoroughly triturated with excess of cold caustic soda solution (10%). The major portion went into solution and the insoluble solid was filtered. The alkaline solution was just neutralised with hydrochloric acid when a solid (3 g.) was obtained. It was purified as above, and found identical with the compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{OEt}$) by a study of its properties and also by analysis.

The alkali-insoluble solid was first purified by solution in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitation with dilute alkali, and it was finally crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. $122\text{--}24^\circ$. It contains chlorine and no arsenic and its extremely poor yield precluded further study and characterisation.

(c). The condensation of *p*-aminophenylarsenoxide with aceto-*p*-phenetidine in presence of phosphorus oxychloride has been studied under the same experimental conditions as described

above. The method of isolation of the reaction products was the same as above. Besides an arsenic-free compound (m.p. 122-24°) which contains chlorine, a compound, proved to be identical with (I, R=OEt) by a comparative study of their properties and by analysis, has been obtained.

(4:4'-Diethoxydiphenyl)-(4:4'-arsenophenyl)acetamidine (II, R=OEt).—The compound (I, R=OEt; 4 g.) in 150 c.c. of water and 8 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid, was reduced by adding, with stirring, 35% hypophosphorus acid (25 g.) and 2 c.c. of 1% aqueous solution of potassium iodide. Soon a precipitate came out and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for about 2 hours. The solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and dissolved in acetic acid. The acetic acid solution was then basified, under cooling, with caustic soda solution, when a cream-coloured solid (2g.) was obtained, which was filtered and washed thoroughly with water. It melts at 178-80° to a brown, viscous mass; it is insoluble in dilute alkali. (Found: As, 22.18. $C_{32}H_{34}O_2N_4As_2$ requires As, 22.83 per cent).

(Phenyl)-(phenyl-4-arsenious acid)-acetamidine (I, R=H).—An intimate mixture of acetanilide (14 g.) and *p*-arsanilic acid (22 g.) was added to phosphorus oxychloride (100 c.c.), and the solution was heated under reflux at 120° for about 4 hours.

From the reaction mixture two compounds, of which one is insoluble in alkali and the other is soluble, have been isolated. The former was purified by solution in acetic acid and precipitation by excess of ammonium hydroxide. It was crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles (5.8 g.), melting at 155-56° and was found to be identical with an authentic sample of 4-anilinoquinaldine (Backeberg, *loc. cit.*).

The alkali-soluble compound (I, R=H) was purified as described previously and was obtained as a colorless solid (6g.) which was dried at 60°-65° *in vacuo*. It melts at 146-48° to a viscous mass. (Found: N, 8.45; As, 22.97. $C_{14}H_{15}O_2N_2As$ requires N, 8.80; As, 23.57 per cent).

(Diphenyl)-(4:4'-arsenophenyl)-acetamidine (II, R=H).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the compound (II, R=OEt). The cream-coloured solid melts at 168-70° to a brown, viscous mass and is insoluble in alkali. (Found: As, 24.05. $C_{30}H_{30}ON_4As_2$ requires As, 24.49 per cent).